

NetDRIVE Annual Report

2025-2026

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Cite as: Juckes, M., Cutting, J., Sparrow, S., Maalouf, A., Smith, G., & Li, L. (2026). NetDRIVE Annual Report, 2025-2026. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20933904>

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACF	Advanced Computing Facility (EPCC's data centre at the University of Edinburgh)
AGM	Annual General Meeting
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARCHER2	UK National Supercomputing Service (successor to ARCHER)
CATS	Climate-Aware Task Scheduler (carbon-aware HPC scheduling tool)
CHEP	Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (conference series)
CIUK	Computing Insight UK (conference)
CLF	Central Laser Facility (STFC)
CLI	Command Line Interface
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DA	Directly Allocated (costs)
DEFRA	Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs
DEICAP	Digital Emissions Integration for Climate Action Planning (NetDRIVE community project)
DI	Directly Incurred (costs)
Diamond	Diamond Light Source (synchrotron facility, STFC)
DIRAC	Distributed Research utilising Advanced Computing (STFC HPC facility)
DNO	Distribution Network Operator
DRI	Digital Research Infrastructure
dRTP	Digital Research Technical Professional
DSIT	Department for Science, Innovation and Technology
ECI	Early Career Investigator
ECR	Early Career Researcher
ENSURE	ENvironmentally SUsustainable digital services and practices for REsearch infrastructures (EU project)
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency (US)
EPCC	Edinburgh Parallel Computing Centre
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FEC	Full Economic Cost
FSE	Faculty of Science and Engineering (University of Manchester)
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
GUILT	Green Usage Impact Logging Tool
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HPC-SIG	High-Performance Computing Special Interest Group
HPE	Hewlett Packard Enterprise
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
ICT	Information and Communication Technology

ISIS	ISIS Neutron and Muon Source (STFC)
ISPACE	Improving Sustainable Performance and Accelerated Computing Efficiency (NetDRIVE community project)
IT	Information Technology
KCL	King's College London
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
LSBU	London South Bank University
MCC	Materials Chemistry Consortium
MRC	Medical Research Council
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
NERC	Natural Environment Research Council
NetDRIVE	Network for Sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise
NHS	National Health Service
NIHR	National Institute for Health and Care Research
NVIDIA	NVIDIA Corporation (hardware vendor)
OERC	Oxford e-Research Centre
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
PAIA	Product Attributes to Impact Algorithm
PCF	Product Carbon Footprint
RAL	Rutherford Appleton Laboratory (STFC)
REACT	Recommendations for Enhancing Adoption of Carbon-footprinting Tool
RI	Research Infrastructure
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SC4RC	Sustainable Computing for Research Computing (conference)
SIG	Special Interest Group
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management (HPC workload manager)
SMART-DRI	Scenario Modelling and Assessment for Research Transition in Digital Research Infrastructure
SSI	Software Sustainability Institute
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council
SusTraIN	Sustainable Training Initiative for NetDRIVE (NetDRIVE community project)
TBC	To Be Confirmed
UCISA	Universities and Colleges Information Systems Association
UK	United Kingdom
UKCEH	UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology
UKNSR	UK Network for Sustainable Research (formerly LEAN)
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
UKRSE	United Kingdom Research Software Engineer (community/Slack)
UNEA-7	United Nations Environment Assembly, 7th session

UPS	Uninterruptible Power Supply
UWE	University of the West of England
VASP	Vienna Ab initio Simulation Package (computational chemistry software)
VM	Virtual Machine
WG	Working Group
WGE	Working Group: Ethics (WG3)
WGMAR	Working Group: Metrics and Reporting (WG4)

Executive Summary

The NetDRIVE project is tackling the intersection of three challenging themes: digital technology, net zero and organisational change. We are framing our work around three key aims: trust, leadership, and progress.

The external factors are rapidly evolving. We are seeing dramatic changes in the climate with some referring to a transition to a new and more dramatic escalation of impacts through large scale systemic changes. The pace and impact of technology change have picked up with the arrival of new artificial intelligence applications which are feeding a drive for more computational resources.

All around us social change is happening, including a strong and diverse societal reaction against policies which derive from net zero and the international commitments associated with the Paris Agreement. At the same time, there is a growing gap between the scientific view of climate change that went into that agreement and the current understanding; if the gap gets any wider it could swallow our civilisation.

Within the NetDRIVE project we are making good progress. We have an active team of champions who are both reaching out into the community and reinforcing each other's work through mutual exchange, exploiting the diversity of the team. The first two community calls have funded a wide range of projects which will advance all elements of the net zero DRI roadmap.

Our community events have generated open and productive discussions on a wide range of topics, both supporting the implementation of the NetDRIVE workplan through community-backed decisions and building trust and connections within the community.

We are now moving into a critical phase of the project, with many activities running, and will encounter the challenge of moving beyond having a portfolio of excellent projects and to creating a community capable of leading the much-needed transformational change.

1. Introduction

NetDRIVE is now in its second year of delivery, operating across three phases through to March 2028 (Figure 1). Year 1 activity — the first 15 months of the programme — has focused on establishing the funded project portfolio, the Champions network, and four working groups, while building the evidence base for net zero transition across UK digital research infrastructure.

For further information contact netdrive@eng.ox.ac.uk or see these online resources:

- Full project workplan: [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14626648](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14626648)
- Project web site : uknetdrive.org

Fourteen projects have been funded across two competitive calls, nine champions are active across partner institutions, and three community meetings have been delivered. The programme has also made early progress on policy engagement, with champions contributing to the DEFRA AI and Energy roundtable, UKRI SPARKhub, and international sustainability networks.

This report describes the achievements of the first 15 months and sets out key priorities for Year 2. Financial details are included in the extended version for internal use and will be redacted from the published report.

Figure 1: NetDRIVE project timeline with three phases.

2. Background

The foundations for this project were laid in two previous projects: the Net Zero DRI Scoping Project (November 2021 to June 2023) and NetDRIVE Stage 1 (July 2024 to February 2025). The scoping project delivered detailed technical recommendations, including a roadmap to net zero. NetDRIVE Stage 1 produced a proposal for the

NetDRIVE2 workplan, submitted for review in November 2024 and subsequently approved. Full details are in the published workplan (Jukes and Sparrow, 2025).

Some initial contractual delays impeded the start of certain activities. Nevertheless, a successful community meeting was held in London to maintain engagement, announce the first funding call, and discuss priorities for the second call.

3. Project Progress

The following sections summarise activity across NetDRIVE's first 15 months.

3.1 Meetings

In its first year NetDRIVE has delivered three community meetings in London, Oxford, and Durham.

The London meeting, held at Queen Mary University London February 18/19, 2025 (<https://zenodo.org/records/14999697>). Discussions at the meeting helped to shape the priorities for funding in the 2nd call for community projects which was launched later in 2025.

The Oxford meeting was held at the Keble College H B Allen Centre on June 12th 2025 (<https://zenodo.org/records/17160867>). The meeting generated valuable feedback on early career participation which led to the inclusion of ring-fenced funds for early career investigators in the second funding call.

The Durham meeting held in the Ogden Centre for Fundamental Physics from September 24th to 26th, 2025, provided a platform for introducing the newly appointed champions to the community (<https://zenodo.org/records/18174566>). Discussions at the meeting led to the launch of three working groups and also produced a set of principles for procurement.

In addition, NetDRIVE ran a sandpit event for early career investigators in Birmingham, 1st-2nd October, 2025.

The NetDRIVE core team also participated in a number of additional events, including:

Event	Date	Venue / Host	Format
UKRI Digital Research Technical Professional NetworkPlus	23 May 2025	Imperial College London	Presentation
CoSeC Energy Efficient Computing Workshop	15–16 Sep 2025	STFC	Presentation

NERC Digital Gathering	7–9 Oct 2025	Cranfield	Recorded presentation
DRI Congress	21–22 Oct 2025	Leeds	Breakout session
DIRAC Day	11 Dec 2025	Stoke on Trent	Presentation

3.2 Community Activities Funded

First Funding Call:

Project	Lead	Institution	Duration
Empowering Digital Researchers: A Series of Best Practice and Tools Guides	Lorna Smith	EPCC	Sep 2025–Aug 2026
ISPACE: Improving Sustainable Performance and Accelerated Computing Efficiency	Adrian Jackson	EPCC	Oct 2025–Sep 2026
NetDRIVE DRI User Summer School	Alastair Basden	Durham University	Sep 2025–Mar 2026

Announcement and guidance: <https://eng.ox.ac.uk/media/estjx3x5/netdrive-first-call-guidance.pdf>

Second Funding Call:

Project	Lead	Institution	Duration	EC
A community hackathon to enable green scheduling	Andrew Walker	University of Oxford	May 2026–Apr 2027	
Dash4Action: Facility Action Plans in Pursuit of a Sustainable UKRI DRI	Alex Owen	Queen Mary University of London	Apr 2026–Mar 2027	
Data sufficiency: A case study of soil data curation, storage, and usage at UKCEH	Carolynne Lord	UKCEH	Apr 2026–Dec 2026	
Digital Emissions Integration for Climate Action Planning (DEICAP)	Polly Eccleston	University of Bristol	Apr 2026–Sep 2027	

Measuring and Effectively Using Emissions Data Across DRI	Jessica Huntley	STFC	May 2026– Apr 2027	
Pathways to Effective Carbon Reductions by Use of Green Scheduling	Michael K Bane	Manchester Metropolitan University	May 2026– Mar 2027	
REACT: Recommendations for Enhancing Adoption of Carbon-footprinting Tools	Liz Ing-Simmons	King's College London	Apr 2026– Mar 2027	EC
SMART-DRI: Scenario Modelling and Assessment for Research Transition in DRI	Zeynep Duygu Tekler	University of Oxford	Mar 2026– Feb 2027	EC
Sustainable Training Initiative for NetDRIVE (SusTrain)	Caterina Doglioni	University of Manchester	Apr 2026– Mar 2027	
Unified Multi-Facility Resources Monitoring Dashboard for Sustainable UK DRI	Loïc Lannelongue	University of Cambridge	Apr 2026– Sep 2027	

Announcement and guidance: <https://eng.ox.ac.uk/netdrive/netdrive-calls/second-funding-call>

3.3 Working Groups

The initiation of four Working Groups (WGs) was discussed and agreed during the AGM in Durham, September 2025. The scope of the WGs was clarified and people identified to take the process forward, including a phase of recruiting an appropriate range of members. In particular, aspects related to evaluation of the NetDRIVE project itself and its success in enhancing community sense of empowerment were taken out of the WG scope and placed back with the co-coordinators, as described in more detail below.

Working Groups will receive funds for meetings, including travel, accommodation, and reservation of meeting rooms from NetDRIVE. Costs in the range £10k to £15k are expected.

Each working group should aim to complete their work by September 2027, earlier if possible, and produce an Advice/Recommendations document which has been through community review. Additional supporting documents may be published. The procedure for advice and recommendations should be based around existing frameworks such as the Research Data Alliance and Health Data Research UK.

A WG on ethics and sustainable progress was proposed but the meeting recommended splitting the sustainable progress element, which relates to the continuity of the NetDRIVE community engagement activity. At the same time the scope of the Working Group on Metrics and Reporting was narrowed for focus on objective metrics of

operational performance. The two elements taken out of these working groups will be picked up in the project reporting led by the co-ordinators, with the support of the integration lead (recruitment in progress). The transparency and community engagement element will be maintained by reviewing the reports in open meetings.

WG1: Short Format Training Material

This working group will create content for a short (10-20 minutes) video tutorial on sustainable research computing, using existing knowledge drawn from the community. The UKRI Environmental Sustainability team will work with contractors to convert the content into a video tutorial which will be freely available online.

WG2: Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses

Digital hardware purchased with UKRI funds should be provided with reliable information about the carbon footprint of manufacture and transport and carry appropriate certification of sustainability measures. In many cases the level of certification and quality of information provided will be limited by the lack of appropriate standards and mechanisms for independent certification. The working group will establish a pragmatic approach building on best practice and emerging standards.

WG3: Ethics (WGE)

WGE was intended to develop an ethical framework for transformational change by reviewing existing frameworks for ethics and exploiting survey results to analyse the human impact of changes impacting on the DRI. The topic has not so far attracted sufficient community engagement.

Further meetings in Year 2 will be arranged to discuss how to take the activity forward, clarifying ethical dimensions, and including potentially reframing it.

WG4: Metrics and Reporting (WGMAR)

WGMAR will develop a framework for monitoring and reporting on community progress towards net zero implementation, with a focus on measurable objective metrics. This will provide essential information on the practical success of actions introduced by NetDRIVE in terms of measurable or inferred impact on emissions.

WGMAR held its kick-off meeting on 6 January to confirm scope, priorities, and expected outputs. The group will develop community-informed guidance and a framework for monitoring and reporting progress towards net zero implementation, focusing on clear, objective metrics to assess the impact of NetDRIVE actions. Initial discussions covered the types of metrics to track (e.g. energy use, carbon and water impacts, and research outputs), their intended use across project lifecycles (including prospective and retrospective assessment), at different levels of aggregation (projects, services, and sector-wide reporting), and the importance of contextualising results to ensure meaningful interpretation.

Initial membership is listed in the table below.

Working Group Title	Initial Membership
WG1: Short Format Training Material	Andy Turner, Liz Ing-Smith, Kirsty Pringle, Lorna Smith
WG2: Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses	Alex Owen, Lorna Smith, Michael Rudgyard, Tom Griffin, Alastair Basden,
WG3: Ethics (WGE)	Erinma Ochu
WG4: Metrics and Reporting (WGMAR)	Loïc Lannelongue, Michael Rudgyard, Emanuele Simili, Alex Owen, Kirsty Pringle, Jessica Huntley, Alistair Basden

4. Engagement and Input from Champions

The Champions for Transformational Change towards Sustainable Research Computing provide leadership across all aspects of technological advance and community transformation relevant to achieving net zero research computing.

4.1 The NetDRIVE Champions

Name	Role	Institution
Loïc Lannelongue	Senior Research Associate (Assistant Research Professor)	University of Cambridge
Michael Rudgyard	Independent consultant	Michael Rudgyard Consultancy
Alex Owen	Senior Physicist Programmer	Queen Mary University of London
Kirsty Pringle	Project Manager	University of Edinburgh, EPCC
Andy Turner	Principal Architect	University of Edinburgh, EPCC
Lorna Smith	Programme Manager	University of Edinburgh, EPCC
Jessica Huntley	Mathematical Research Software Engineer	STFC
Erinma Ochu	Wallscourt Associate Professor, Immersive Media	UWE Bristol
Liz Ing-Simmons	Senior Research Software Engineer	King's College London

Jessica Huntley and Liz Ing-Simmons hold Early Career Champion roles.

4.2 Monthly Meetings

The Champions monthly meetings commenced in November 2025. The meeting provides a regular opportunity for coordination and engagement among champions. Figure 2 illustrates the role of these meetings within the overall project management structure.

Agenda items include updates on progress in relation to the champions’ objectives, discussion of champions’ involvement in community activities, and oversight of ongoing initiatives. The meeting also includes discussion of upcoming events and forward planning activities.

Figure 2: NetDRIVE Governance Structure.

The NERC Project Board holds quarterly meetings. The Project Executive Group is located in Oxford and meets every week. The Project Operations Team, consisting of champions and the core team has been meeting monthly since October. The Review Panel is convened as needed to review proposals for community activities. The Network General Assembly is taking place through a series of community meetings: three held in 2025 and three planned for 2026. The Community Leadership Team, with investigators from the funded community activities, will be convened in 2026.

Across the first 15 months of the programme, the nine champions have collectively delivered substantive activity across three broad areas.

On external engagement and advocacy, Loïc Lannelongue presented at over a dozen conferences and workshops across Europe and North America, contributed to the DEFRA AI and Energy roundtable, and co-developed Green DiSC and a multi-facility carbon monitoring dashboard.

On training and community building, Andy Turner led HPC emissions modelling and RSE community sessions, Kirsty Pringle developed community-of-practice frameworks across institutions, and Jessica Huntley organised sustainable computing workshops at STFC and within the CoSeC network.

On policy and supply chain, Michael Rudgyard conducted detailed supplier research across major DRI hardware vendors (Dell, HPE, Lenovo, NVIDIA, Supermicro) in support of WG2 procurement work, and Alex Owen is progressing UKRI supply chain sustainability clauses.

Erinma Ochu has developed the ethical and cultural change framing for the programme through storytelling and immersive media approaches.

Lorna Smith has additionally undertaken distinctive biodiversity work at the EPCC data centre site.

Full reports from each champion are presented in Annex B.

5. Context and Boundary Conditions

This section sets out some key external developments which will influence decision making around net zero.

5.1 Operational Emissions: Power Supply

The carbon footprint of the operational power demand remains a central issue to the DRI. Publication of the UK “Clean Power 2030 Action Plan: A new era of clean electricity”¹ provides some clarity about the next phase of decarbonising the UK power grid. This will involve continued investment in solar and wind power generation to reduce dependency on gas. These renewable sources will provide plentiful cheap power but cannot provide the continuity that many users have taken for granted over recent decades.

The lack of continuity in renewable supply is being addressed through 5 additional lines of investment:

- Grid-scale battery installations providing high capacity for periods of up to several hours;
- New nuclear capacity to replace plants and maintain overall nuclear generation capacity;

¹ <https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/677bc80399c93b7286a396d6/clean-power-2030-action-plan-main-report.pdf>

- New hydrogen infrastructure to store energy, provide additional distribution capacity, create the potential for additional imports, and expand potential for exporting excess;
- Retained gas generation capacity to be used for very limited periods;
- Pricing and other incentives to create, encourage, reward flexibility in user demand.

There is considerable uncertainty about the speed of deployment and final costs of the first three items (grid-scale batteries, new nuclear and hydrogen infrastructure) remain subject to many uncertainties but there is a clear and robust expectation that continuity of supply will come at a cost and that this will create risks and opportunities for users. In particular, it will be possible to obtain pricing advantages through flexibility in location and time periods of operation.

The scale of the potential savings is revealed in the UK Policy Paper on “Delivering AI Growth Zones”, which specifies savings of up to £24 per MWh depending on location. For a 20MW supercomputer operating close to 8,000 hours per year, that would translate into a £3.8m annual saving in power costs.

It is worth noting that the scale of investment flowing into UK research computing is considerably smaller than investment in public cloud, and the footprint will be correspondingly smaller. The community is, however, committed to ensuring that these resources are run sustainably and, if possible, exporting best practice to those running larger systems.

5.2 Embedded Emissions: Supply Chain, Maintenance and Waste

The supply chain emissions of our computers are generally considered to be dominated by the manufacturing phase, though there is considerable uncertainty around the footprint of materials going into the manufacturing process.

The complexity and scale of the global market pose many challenges, particularly in making it hard to identify where UKRI and UKRI funded service providers can exert influence or make constructive pro-environmental choices. It is also clear that there is movement towards a greener supply chain which is being driven by a far broader base of consumer concerns. Major suppliers, such as DELL and HP, provide estimates of carbon footprint for an increasing range of products, although generally only for default consumer configurations and with many caveats about uncertainties and scope of applicability.

Despite the limitations of the supply chain information that is available, the trend towards greater clarity shows that there is a general will to implement change and

NetDRIVE champions are engaging with UKRI to develop guidance that will enable UKRI procurements to exploit and support this change.

5.3 The Balance of Emissions

In addition to power supply and supply chain, the DRI has emissions associated with running offices, connected devices of users (in as far as the DRI business model is dependent on users having and operating certain classes of devices), and business travel. The concept of net zero also assumes that it will be possible for a certain level of residual emissions to be compensated for through active removal of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

The most widely exploited mechanism for compensatory removals to date has been offsetting through a range of biosphere interventions, primarily tree planting. There are, however, severe doubts about the net benefits of such interventions: do they actually result in net removal of carbon from the atmosphere or are they simply replacing one biosphere process with another? For this reason, UKRI does not currently support offsetting, and it is not an eligible cost item on UKRI grants².

Direct removal of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere independent of the biosphere has been demonstrated to be possible, but the demonstration also provided greater clarity about the limitations of the existing technology, particularly around the high capital and operational costs of the infrastructure.

There are also challenges in other areas, such as aviation, where hoped-for advances which might enable a smooth green transition, with limited behaviour change, have failed to materialise³.

It is clear in the public debate that there are those who feel that the accumulation of such challenges imply that current net zero targets are unrealistic, while others feel that the targets are backed by an urgency which demands that such obstacles be overcome at all costs. A similar range of views, though expressed with greater care than the louder elements of the public debate, can be found in the research community.

5.4 Urgency

Recent assessment shows that the global mean surface temperature is very likely to pass 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels by 2030 and is rising at a rate which will pass 2 °C

² <https://www.ukri.org/publications/ukri-position-statement-on-carbon-offsetting/ukri-position-statement-on-carbon-offsetting/> [accessed 9 February 2026]

³ Velocopter flew demonstration flights of an electrically powered helicopter and had aims to launch an initial service for the Paris Olympics, but filed for bankruptcy in 2024. Eviation Alice flew a prototype in 2022 but laid-off most of their staff in 2025. Both companies had, in earlier plans, ambitions to transition from using Lithium-Ion batteries to a new battery technology with higher power density, but candidate technologies have failed to achieve the necessary maturity.

above pre-industrial levels by 2050 (Forster et al. 2025). Improved understanding of the societal and environmental risks associated with rising global temperatures imply that the impacts of passing these boundaries will be more severe than previously thought (Lenton et al, 2025 [grey literature]), including significant risks of biosphere collapse leading to accelerated growth in the atmospheric burden of greenhouse gasses.

6. Financials Summary

NetDRIVE2 carries a total award value of £4,177,255.85 at Full Economic Cost. %0% of this in in a flexible fund, of which 84% (£1,756k) is to be redistributed to community projects. The remainder of the flexible fund finances the management of the fund. A further £849k is for the champions, and £203k is to support community activities. The table below gives a summary of the status in these categories.

Project Finances	Committed	Remaining	Commentary
Flexible Fund	£1,097k	£658k	Remaining funds to be distributed in 3 rd call.
Other	£40k	£163k	Spending on travel, workshops, and facilitation is below expected values. Some of this will be used to recruit a project support officer at Oxford.
Champions	£849k	£130k	Some funds to be used for one or two additional early career champions. Some to pay for increased staff time needed by Martin (50% instead of 40% budgeted for).

At the 15-month point — 38% of the programme timeline — expenditure is broadly on track, with some variation by partner. Oxford has spent approximately 22% of its allocation to date, representing a modest underspend relative to the programme timeline, though this partly reflects the staged onboarding of staff during the first year. The NCAS fund shows 74% committed, driven primarily by the community projects strand (£1,943,624.11 allocated, with 83% committed following the first and second funding calls). Figures for the STFC allocation are pending and will be included in the full confidential annex.

Full partner-level expenditure detail, including the cost breakdown by category and allocation by partner, is provided in the Confidential Annex.

7. Future Prospects

7.1 Facilitation Plans for Early Career Investigators

As an initial step, and as part of ongoing activity, work related to Early Career Investigator (ECI) facilitation has focused on mapping existing NetDRIVE structures and identifying opportunities for meaningful engagement. This has included an initial review of current community activities, Working Group scopes, and Champions' discussions in order to understand where ECI participation could be most effective and where additional support mechanisms may be required.

Based on this initial mapping, plans are being developed to support more structured and inclusive engagement of ECIs across NetDRIVE activities. This includes identifying appropriate entry points for ECIs within Working Groups, community meetings, and funded projects, as well as considering how facilitation can help ECIs navigate technical, organisational, and cultural aspects of sustainable digital research infrastructure.

Future activity will focus on strengthening connections between ECIs, Champions, and project leads, with the aim of supporting knowledge exchange and enabling ECIs to contribute to cross-cutting discussions. Particular attention will be given to themes that span multiple areas of activity, including ethics, transparency, community engagement, and the human impacts of transformational change in digital research infrastructure.

Plans also include aligning ECI facilitation with broader community processes, such as open reporting and review mechanisms, to ensure that early career perspectives are visible and inform ongoing NetDRIVE development. As these plans progress, facilitation approaches will be refined in response to emerging needs and feedback from the community.

In addition, initial planning is underway for the development of an induction programme aimed at supporting the integration of Early Career Investigators and social science champions into NetDRIVE and the wider UK Digital Research Infrastructure and Net Zero landscape. The proposed programme is intended to provide a concise introduction to NetDRIVE's objectives and the UK DRI ecosystem, support connections with relevant technical leads and peer networks, and enable early confidence and meaningful participation. Current planning is exploring a structured approach informed by a "knowledge translation and exchange framework", combining orientation, topic-specific alignment, and clear integration pathways, with the aim of creating a scalable and repeatable model for future cohorts.

Looking ahead, the upcoming NetDRIVE community meeting, "*Creating a New Reality: A Sustainable Digital Transformation*", scheduled for 22–23 April 2026 in Oxford, will be used as an opportunity to support Early Career Investigator engagement. Planning includes the launch of a call for abstracts and poster presentations, with specific

encouragement for early career submissions. This is intended to provide accessible opportunities for ECIs to share work, increase visibility within the community, and engage with NetDRIVE themes in a supportive setting.

7.2 Forthcoming Community Meetings

We are aiming for two multi-day community meetings in 2026. Venues and dates should be advertised 6 months in advance to allow potential delegates time to adjust schedules. The first has taken place in Oxford in April, and the second will be held in Bristol in November. The NetDRIVE project will pay reasonable costs, including room hire and staff time for the institution hosting the meetings.

Meetings should combine discussion of challenges specific to NetDRIVE with broader themes which impact on the NetDRIVE objectives.

7.3 Cultural Change (including annual meeting)

The annual cultural change gathering will take place in Bristol during the first week of November 2026. The theme will explore how digital technology is transforming the research community, and how that transformation can be harnessed to accelerate the transition to a fair and equitable society.

8. Gaps to be addressed in 2026

8.1 Social science engagement

NetDRIVE has a clear need for engagement with the social sciences in order to benefit from academic knowledge of issues around culture change and transformational change. Opportunities were created in both the first and second calls but failed to attract proposals. Initial enquiries among colleagues in the social science sector suggests that there were issues with both the structure and the communication of these opportunities. A ring-fenced opportunity for the social science sector will be included in the third call after further engagement with the community.

We also need to identify community meetings at which we can engage with the social science community.

8.2 Communication plan

Effective communication is central to NetDRIVE's ability to build and sustain an engaged community across a geographically distributed network of champions, funded projects, and partner institutions. As the programme grows, ensuring that the right information reaches the right audiences through the right channels becomes increasingly important.

NetDRIVE currently operates five communication channels:

Channel	Details
Website	Announcements and general project information: https://uknetdrive.org/
Contact email	Queries to the core team: netdrive@eng.ox.ac.uk
Distribution list	Open sign-up: netdrive-all@maillist.ox.ac.uk
Champions list	Private discussion list for champions
NetDRIVE forum	https://sustainable-research-computing.mn.co/

There is some duplication between the roles of the email list and the forum, and many features of the forum are not being fully exploited. In the coming year we need to devise a more systematic way of exploiting both these tools and our expanding network.

8.3 Robust call workflow

The NetDRIVE team has faced considerable challenges in the implementation of the funding calls, aggravated by the need to maintain a range of parallel activities at the same time, particularly the community meetings.

Guidance for projects conducting flexible funding calls is incomplete, though we have now been given access to draft UKRI guidance documents and will be making use of these in the third funding call.

ANNEX A: References

- Beard, N. (2023). Net zero computing: scoping UKRI's journey to sustainable digital research infrastructure. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8203117>
- Juckes, M., & Sparrow, S. (2025). Net-Zero Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise: Open Workplan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14626648>
- Juckes, M., Bane, M., Bulpett, J., Cartmell, K., MacFarlane, M., MacRae, M., Owen, A., Pascoe, C., & Townsend, P. (2023). Sustainability in Digital Research Infrastructure: UKRI Net Zero DRI Scoping Project final technical report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>
- Juckes, M., Sparrow, S., Smith, G., & Li, L. (2026). NetDRIVE Workshop Durham University, September 24-26, 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174566>
- Otty, L. (2025, September 24). Greening digital research in the arts and humanities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174242>
- Basden, A. (2025, September 24). HPC at Durham. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174359>
- Farley, M. (2025, September 24). UKRI DRI Sustainability Plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174422>
- Forster, P. M., et al/: Indicators of Global Climate Change 2024: annual update of key indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence, Earth Syst. Sci. Data, 17, 2641–2680, <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-17-2641-2025>, 2025.
- Friday, A. (2025, September 24). Embedding ICT (ir)responsibly? Toward cultural change. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18174483>
- Lenton, T. M., Milkoreit, M., Willcock, S., Abrams, J. F., Armstrong McKay, D. I., Buxton, J. E., Donges, J. F., Loriani, S., Wunderling, N., Alkemade, F., Barrett, M., Constantino, S., Powell, T., Smith, S. R., Boulton, C. A., Pinho, P., Dijkstra, H. A. Pearce-Kelly, P., Roman- Cuesta, R. M., Dennis, D. (eds), 2025, The Global Tipping Points Report 2025. University of Exeter, Exeter, UK. ©The Global Tipping Points Report 2025, University of Exeter, UK. <https://global-tipping-points.org/download/1418/>

ANNEX B: Champion Reports

The following reports have been submitted by NetDRIVE Champions for the period September 2025 to March 2026.

Jessica Huntley — Embedding Sustainable Computing Best Practice

Author: Jessica Huntley

Title: Embedding Sustainable Computing Best Practice

In September 2025, I was an organiser for the CoSeC Energy Efficient Computing workshop, an event designed to share knowledge and start conversations around making energy efficient choices. A wide variety of speakers were invited to highlight the importance of cross-discipline collaboration and the event attracted both national and international experts. A white paper to record the topics and discussions from the event is currently being prepared.

I am in the early stages of organising an event in collaboration with Dawn Geatches (Innovate UK Business Connect). The focus of this event will be sustainable AI, bringing together specialists in AI, mathematics, and software engineering, to work on tackling specific challenges posed by industry partners.

Internally at STFC, I organised a workshop which took place in September 2025, to share progress on sustainability initiatives and raise awareness of NetDRIVE, highlighting the second funding call. One of the workshop sessions focused on discussing project ideas and, as a result, a cross-departmental team was formed, developing a community project proposal focused on training. Starting in June 2026, the project will produce training modules focused on effectively measuring and using carbon emissions data, with tailored content for different DRI stakeholders. Through my NetDRIVE champion role, I will be looking to align the work of this project with the other funded initiatives.

The STFC workshop also included a session on Green DiSC, encouraging teams across the organisation to work towards a recognised sustainability standard. Following concerns from some of my colleagues about the relevance of the criteria for those running platforms and service, I joined a working group, led by Loïc Lannelongue, for developing a new Green DiSC criteria stream for Research Computing Infrastructure Teams.

Within STFC's Scientific Computing Department, I am committed to developing and proposal sustainability-focused projects for graduates and the working group that I lead is currently supporting three early career projects. These are focused on measuring the carbon footprint of computing services run by the department and how to report data to users, and I will be encouraging graduates to submit poster abstracts for the upcoming

NetDRIVE meeting. I have also promoted the sustainability strategy framework established by the departmental working group, presenting a poster at the CoSeC conference in December. This attracted attention from other institutions seeking to adopt similar approaches, and I plan to publish accessible resources to share the outcomes from Scientific Computing’s working group more widely.

At the UKRI level, I have been engaging with the Environmental Sustainability Programme team, having had a discussion with Martin Farley about SPARKHub and potential contributions I could make. I am also in the process of arranging a meeting with Susan Simon to discuss the environmental impact of computing.

Additionally, I have joined the NetDRIVE working group on metrics and reporting, attending a kick-off meeting in January 2026. Going forward I will be contributing to the development of a working document outlining key quantities to track and guidance on how these should be used.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
15th–16th September 2025	Organiser of the CoSeC Energy Efficient Computing Workshop, invited Martin to speak on NetDRIVE.	https://www.numerical.rl.ac.uk/events/workshop-on-green-computing/
29th September 2025	Organiser of an internal STFC Environmental Sustainability Workshop – focused session to discuss NetDRIVE funding call and opportunities for collaboration.	
3rd December 2025	CoSeC Annual Conference – poster presented on 'Embedding Energy-Efficient Computing Best Practices', referencing NetDRIVE.	https://doi.org/10.5286/stfcconf.2026002

Loïc Lanelongue — Expanding the Sustainable DRI Network, Tool Building, and Stakeholder Engagement

Author: Loïc Lanelongue

Title: Expanding the sustainable DRI network, tool building, and stakeholders engagement

This covers the period from start of September 2025 to March 2026 (planned events for the February – March period).

In this first period of the NetDRIVE Champion role, I have split my time between raising awareness about NetDRIVE and sustainable DRI, training researchers in sustainable computing, and leading initiative providing tools and frameworks in this space. Raising awareness and training was mostly done through talks that I have delivered across Europe and some outside of Europe (e.g. Canada). I have also continued to develop tools and projects aligned with NetDRIVE stated goals, such as the Green Algorithms tools (an HPC monitoring dashboard in particular) and the Green DiSC certification. In particular, in response to limitations identified in NetDRIVE meetings, we expanded Green DiSC to better fit with HPC operators. I also started to Chair the NetDRIVE working group on Metrics and Reporting, and contributed to the Working Group on Training.

Below is a more detailed list of the different activities.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
2025-10-14	Participation in the Oxford x DEFRA roundtable to advise DEFRA on issues relevant to sustainable AI ahead of the UNEA-7 conference.	
2025-10-22	Participation in the MRC/NHS/NIHR Sustainable Healthcare conference to engage with the health research community on sustainable computing.	https://engagementhub.ukri.org/mrc-events/conference-on-research-outcomes-in-environmental-s/
2025-11-05	Presentation at the LEAN (now called UKNSR) meeting in Manchester, alongside Kirsty Pringle and Lorna Smith, to connect with the sustainable DRI community.	https://events.manchester.ac.uk/event/event:n10k-mgrntcmx-6j16cg/towards-sustainable-digital-research
2025–2026	Organisation of the SC4RC conference for an international event dedicated to sustainable computing.	www.sc4rc.org
2025–2026	Creation of a Green DiSC working group for Research Computing Infrastructure, which overlaps largely with NetDRIVE remit.	
2025–2026	Green DiSC development. NetDRIVE angle: directly supports sustainable DRI.	

2025-11-26	Talk at the Frugal AI days in Grenoble. Presentation of the network, raise awareness, European-level engagement.	https://jraf-2025.sciencesconf.org
2025-11-28	Panel at the Royal Academy of Engineering conference. Presentation of the network, engagement with engineering leadership.	https://raeng.org.uk/events/2025/november/award-excellence-community-conference-2025/
2025-12-05	MSCA lunchtime talk about green computing and their new Green Charter. Contribution to the digital components of the MSCA Green Charter.	https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/event/msca-lunchtime-conversation-making-ai-sustainable-how-can-we-m
2025–2026	Engagement with UKRI-driven SPARKhub and facilitated the integration of Green DiSC into it.	
2025-12-06	Keynote at EurIPS in Copenhagen on green computing. Highlighted the network to researchers across Europe.	https://rethinking-ai.github.io
2025–2026	Chair the NetDRIVE Working Group on Metrics and Reporting.	
2025–2026	Contribution to NetDRIVE Training working group as a reviewer.	
2026-01-16	Talk at the Crick with Kirsty Pringle and Lorna Smith on sustainable computing and highlighting NetDRIVE.	
2026-01-19	MRC Sustainability Seminar: attended and presented. Cross-UKRI engagement on sustainable DRI.	https://www.ukri.org/events/mrc-es-putting-sustainable-science-into-practice/
2026-01-21	Expert Engagement Group on Climate and AI, 2026 AI Summit hosted by India. Engagement with policymakers on sustainable computing.	
2026-01-28	Annual lecture at University of Toronto on sustainable computing. Expansion of the sustainable DRI international network.	https://temertymedicine.utoronto.ca/event/sustainability-challenge-modern-computational-science-loic-lannelongue-jan-28

2026-02-04	Present on green computing and NetDRIVE at the University of Birmingham. Raise awareness and broaden network.	
2026-02-24	Host a roundtable with Kirsty Pringle at the Cancer Research UK Annual Data Conference in Edinburgh to discuss sustainable computing.	
2025–2026	Applied for a NetDRIVE Community grant with Andy Turner; working on a multi-facility monitoring dashboard.	

Erinma Ochu — Storytelling Champion

Author: Erinma Ochu

Title: Storytelling champion (and Wallscourt Associate Professor, Immersive Media)

Following participation in the community gathering in Durham, I agreed to lead the newly formed Ethics and Sustainability group within the NetDRIVE initiative. However after consultation at the event, the Sustainability element was later removed. With no additional champions joining the Ethics Group this requires a reconfiguration. This prompted deeper consideration of how ethics is currently framed within the network and how and where it might sit across disciplinary boundaries. Ethical reflection remains critical to the overall agenda, but it may need to be grounded more explicitly using a cross-disciplinary remit that draws on social science and community engagement processes to realise its full potential. I contributed to reviewing the procurement group’s output.

At present, the main epistemic focus for NetDRIVE centres on data collection and monitoring. While important, this risks limiting engagement to STEM disciplines and may not mobilise the broader cultural change the initiative seeks to achieve. Addressing this challenge will likely require an interdisciplinary framework - one capable of bridging ethical reflection with creative and experiential practice. Storytelling and lived experience offer a potential route to build this bridge, establishing common ground and facilitating collaboration across fields.

During the Durham trip, a visit to a local data centre made clear the tangible environmental and social impacts of data infrastructures. This experience highlighted the urgency for change and revealed the value of sensory, place-based engagements in awareness raising. These insights will be built into how storytelling in relation to culture change is developed further, e.g. through the podcast and the annual summit.

My contribution as champion is focused on storytelling as a tool for mobilising change. After conversations with the Principal Investigator (PI), it was agreed that we begin with a reflective process of ‘inner journeys’ - a period of facilitated inquiry into the emotional and cultural complexities of working toward systemic change. This phase is currently underway and due for completion in April 2026. It is intended to create the psychological and relational grounding necessary for outward-facing storytelling and advocacy work.

At UWE Bristol, I have been engaging with internal UWE and Bristol networks to identify opportunities for galvanising change and embedding NetDRIVE within existing sustainability and cultural change efforts. Through the Head of Sustainability, and School of Arts Research Dean, I began mapping potential connections across faculties and staff communities. This mapping work created the opportunity to contribute to a session for 50 undergraduate documentary students on climate storytelling in relation to netzero (and digital production). The course uses materials from Albert (wearealbert.org) to illustrate how principles of net zero can be integrated into digital production, offering a model for practice-based learning. It also opened up connections to those championing change through practice in Computing, Engineering and The Arts, and is now creating opportunities to build approaches into job descriptions and funding bids with researchers and support staff.

My approach is asset-based and relational - beginning with listening to understand where individuals and groups are already active (or not), and building from existing strengths. As UWE Bristol prepares to host the 2026 Autumn Gathering on culture change during Green Week (beginning 1 November 2026), this approach is helping to nurture trust, recognise existing leadership, and consolidate a community of practice committed to meaningful, interdisciplinary climate action.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
08/09/2025	EarthWatch Science Camp – introduced NetDRIVE within storytelling session at annual science camp with 15 environmental scientists.	https://figshare.com/articles/presentation/ScienceCamp_Storytelling_session/30264628?file=58450618
24/09/2025	NetDRIVE champion session.	https://figshare.com/articles/presentation/Storytelling_champion_-_NetDRIVE/30207565?file=58249237
7–9 October 2025	NERC Digital Gathering, Cranfield – recorded presentation. Contribution included in overarching presentation,	

	effective in triggering attention within the wider community.	
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Alex Owen — Champion Report September 2025 to March 2026

Author: Dr R A Owen (“Alex Owen”)

Title: Champion Report September 2025 to March 2026

With the commencement of my champion role in September I used my one day a week for project startup and to prepare for and attend the first NetDRIVE AGM. In October I helped to run the 2 day Early Career Sandpit event in Birmingham which led to the formation of two project groups which each submitted successful NetDRIVE flexible funding proposals. I also joined the NetDRIVE sustainable procurement Working Group and made significant contributions to the draft document, work which continued into November. In November I also prepared and gave a guest Lecture entitled “Sustainable Computing: Carbon Costs & UKRI NetZero DRI” to students on an applied AI apprenticeship at Queen Mary University of London.

December saw me attend the HPC-SIG un-conference event in Manchester where I proposed and chaired a well-attended sustainability session in which many people were engaged and eager to exchange ideas and learn about our NetZero work. The annual STFC Scientific Computing conference “Computing Insight UK” had invited NetDRIVE PI’s to speak in a DRI session. It fell to me to represent NetDRIVE with a short presentation and panel session. There was also a hastily arraigned DRI breakout at which I also represented NetDRIVE. January has seen the initiation of the NetDRIVE metrics working group of which I am a member, and I have submitted a NetDRIVE poster abstract to the 28th Conference on Computing in High Energy and Nuclear Physics (CHEP 2026).

In February I will continue to contribute to the two working groups and prepare abstracts for further talks and posters, with the aim of disseminating the work of NetDRIVE more widely. I have secured a place at the DRI Retreat in Manchester in March 2026 where I intend to represent NetDRIVE and input and where appropriate lead discussions on sustainable computing.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
December 2025	HPC-SIG	Report expected at: https://hpc-sig.org.uk/meeting-reports/
December 2025	CIUK	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17936515

Kirsty Pringle — Building Communities of Digital Research Professionals to Achieve Net Zero DRI

Author: Kirsty Pringle

Title: Building communities of digital research professionals to achieve Net Zero DRI.

During this initial period as a NetDRIVE Champion, I have focused on supporting community engagement and increasing awareness of environmental sustainability within the digital research professional community.

Green RSE SIG

I lead the Green Research Software Engineering Special Interest Group (<https://socirse.github.io/green-sig/>), which is run in collaboration with the Society of RSEs. The Green RSE SIG explores how RSEs can help reduce the environmental impact of research software, including by delivering training, adopting and championing best practises and advocating for environmentally sustainable approaches. The steering committee is made up of 10 RSEs from across the community, we meet monthly and work to better understand how we can support the RSE community to achieve our aims.

In September, the Green RSE SIG held a community session at the annual Research Software Engineering Conference to better understand what the role of a “Green RSE” might entail and how effective it could be in reducing the environmental impact of digital research. Outputs from this session were shared through a conference blog post ([link](#)).

The group has had a poster accepted for the upcoming Collaborations Workshop in Belfast, and a workshop submission is currently under review. In addition to formal meetings, the Green RSE SIG maintains an active channel on the UKRSE slack forum with 85 members, which supports ongoing discussion and resource sharing.

During RSECon25, the SIG introduced the first Green RSE Award, which was presented to Andy Turner (University of Edinburgh). The award, sponsored by the Software Sustainability Institute ([link](#)), is designed to raise awareness and recognise those that have

made a significant contribution in this field. We have confirmed funding in place to support the award for the next two years.

Training

Part-funded through a parallel project, Greening Digital Research (PI: Weronika Fillinger), I have been working to better understand existing skills gaps that are hindering the transition towards reducing the environmental impact of digital research. This work has informed the Champion role by identifying training needs, as well as community strengths and weaknesses. This work will contribute to an updated version of the DIRECT Training Framework, in which “green” skills are highlighted (). In addition, I am part of a working group that is developing introductory training materials for the SparkHUB platform (with Martin Farley, UKRI) and an advisor on the funded NetDRIVE community project “Sustainable Training Initiative for NetDRIVE (SusTrain)”.

Community Events

As part of my community role, I will run online community events to inform and raise awareness. I am in discussions with the Alan Turing Institute (), which runs a regular online “fireside chats” series. These short, accessible events are a mix of talks and panel discussions. We plan to collaborate to run a series of “green” fireside chats. This approach benefits from using an existing format and structure and will build on the engaged community supported by the Alan Turing Institute to reach new audiences.

Green DiSC

Finally, I have a small supporting role in the Green DiSC initiative, led by fellow champion Loïc Lannelongue (<https://greendisc.org/>). As part of this work, I am leading the Software Sustainability Institute’s application for the Green DiSC Bronze Award. This has involved developing a new environmental sustainability strategy for the institute (<https://www.software.ac.uk/environmental-sustainability-policy>). In addition, I have met with several groups interested in Green DiSC certification to provide information about the requirements and process involved.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
3 September 2025	Press release for the Green DiSC project, SSI blog. Supporting work of NetDRIVE Champion Lannelongue.	https://www.software.ac.uk/news/green-disc-helping-researchers-make-computational-research-more-sustainable
3 September 2025	Press release for the Green DiSC project. Supporting work of NetDRIVE Champion Lannelongue.	https://www.ed.ac.uk/news/roadmap-developed-for-greener-data-science

September 2025	Green RSE SIG community session at RSECon25. Core part of Pringle NetDRIVE Champion work.	https://virtual.oxfordabstracts.com/event/75166/submission/25
September 2025	Poster: 'It's time to decarbonise digital research.' Won a poster prize. Included Green RSE SIG and NetDRIVE.	https://media.ed.ac.uk/media/Kirsty+Pringle+RSECon25
24 November 2025	Blog summarising output from the community session at RSECon25 run by the Green RSE SIG.	https://www.software.ac.uk/blog/rses-can-lead-sustainable-research-we-cant-just-rely-their-goodwill
30 January 2026	Reviewed and contributed to sustainability course developed by Lannelongue. Recorded a video on the Green RSE SIG for the course.	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/online/courses/sustainable-computing-in-science/what-can-we-do/community-and-grassroots-i
January 2026	Advisor on the funded NetDRIVE training project SusTraIN.	https://uknetdrive.org/netdrive-community-projects
11 February 2026	Greening Digital Research / DIRECT Framework hackathon to implement findings from the green scoping into the DIRECT framework.	

Michael Rudgyard — Supply Chain and Metrics Champion

Author: M Rudgyard

Title: NetDrive Champion Update (Sep 2025 – Mar 2026)

I started my tenure as a NetDRIVE champion at the annual Workshop in Durham in September 2025. This served as a good introduction – both to the renewed project as well as to the other Champions and Stakeholders.

I volunteered to join two working groups at the annual workshop: WG2 – Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses, and WG4 – Metrics and Reporting (WGMAR). I focussed most of my activities in quarter four 2025 on WG2, which aimed to deliver relevant clauses for research infrastructure procurement that could subsequently be distributed by UKRI. My specific focus was to get a better understanding of embedded carbon in IT equipment, so as to provide advice on what might be reasonable (and deliverable) to ask of suppliers as part of a procurement exercise.

Although the working group was already aware that certain manufacturers (such as Dell and HPE) provide Product Carbon Footprints (or PCFs) for some of, or most of, their products, there was much less understanding of what exactly these meant, and what

other manufacturers provide and where to find this information. In order to ensure a level playing field for the main suppliers, I decided to reach out to a number of suppliers and was successful in getting (much of) the requested information from Dell, HPE, Lenovo, NetApp, NVIDIA and Supermicro; in some cases (eg. Supermicro) I was able to speak to senior people in the sustainability team.

My findings indicate that most suppliers provide, or are able to provide (on request). PCFs for the main products that are used in UKRI large-scale computing procurements. Some companies are able to provide good coverage of their products, whereas others (eg. Supermicro and NVIDIA) have more limited (public) coverage, but are planning to increase product coverage or may provide specific information on request. It seems that all manufacturers take the same approach to the generation of PCF documentation, which uses a model based on the Product Attributes to Impact Algorithm (PAIA) – this is the result of a collaboration between MIT and Quantis to provide “a streamlined methodology for ICT product footprinting, a suite of simplified online tools, and a consortium of ICT companies”. Given the complexity of IT supply chains, it is perhaps unsurprising that the industry relies on supply chain and resource modelling to define PCFs and that there is very significant error in the approximate Carbon Footprints that they provide.

The findings of WG2 were delivered to UKRI and a final review is currently taking place. I am also completing a brief document that summarises my findings to publish on the NetDRIVE website as a community resource.

The first meeting for WG4 took place in December 2025, with a follow up meeting that will take place shortly.

Other activities that I have been involved with include a presentation to the UCISA Digital Sustainability working group, monthly Champions meetings, a meeting with UKRI to discuss UKRI strategy and how we might best influence best practise for carbon reductions, as well as meetings to plan the Oxford event in April 2026.

Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
24–26 September 2025	NetDRIVE Workshop Durham University.	https://zenodo.org/records/18174566
21 October 2025	UCISA Digital Sustainability WG. Digital Impact: Cutting Carbon in UK Higher Education and Research.	https://www.ucisa.ac.uk/Events/2025/October/Digital-impact

Lorna Smith — Champion Report, September 2025–March 2026

Author: Lorna Smith, EPCC, The University of Edinburgh

Title: Champion Report for the period 1st Sept 2025-March 2026 for Lorna Smith, EPCC, The University of Edinburgh

My champion role has three main activities: to explore the rebound effect and the tension between climate needs and maximising impact and benefits from DRI facilities; to develop evidence-based recommendations and best practice on the use of low carbon supply chains in procurement of DRI and associated support facilities; and to promote biodiversity literacy and nature positivity, developing recommendations to halt biodiversity loss. During this initial phase of my champions role I have engaged and initiated activities across all three areas.

I have been actively engaged in the NetDRIVE working group “WG1: Short Format Training Material”. In this, I have been working with a group of fellow champions and Martin Farley from UKRI to develop a short training course on the emissions associated with the Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI). This group has met regularly, there is a first draft of the course material. This is being refined while the design is procured. This training includes a short section on the rebound effect, contributing to my activity in this area.

I have also been active within “WG2: Supply Chain Environmental Sustainability Clauses”, which directly relates to my activities around low carbon supply chains and procurement. This work has again been with a group of fellow champions and with Martin Farley. The group has been working on a set of Environmental Sustainability criteria for inclusion in the procurement of digital hardware. There is a draft of this document which is currently out for review and comment.

I have also presented on the environmental sustainability initiatives at our Advanced Computing Facility at two different events. The first was at the UKNSR Towards Sustainable Digital Research meeting in Manchester in December 2025 and the second at The Francis Crick Institute in London in January 2026. This generated a lot of interest and engagement.

The next National Supercomputing Service will be housed in an extended computer room 4. During the planning application for this extension I have been actively involved in defining site biodiversity plans and improvements, together with the data centre manager and landscaping team. As a result new areas of the site will include native hedgerows, wildlife corridors, felled wood habitats, an orchard and wildflower areas. A key success has been the movement of the contractor accommodation from a natural wildlife rich area to an existing area of hard standing, protecting a significant amount of biodiversity on site.

In March 2026, I am one of the organisers of an event title “Championing Green Digital Research”, an event associated with the ARCHER2 Celebration of Science. The aim of the workshop is to provide insight into and expand on recent efforts to understand what skills are needed to empower researchers and other digital research technical professionals to make and advocate for positive impact in using DRI for research. This event is being organised in combination with the ARCHER2 service and the UKRI Research Infrastructure Network+ programmes CHARTED and DisCourSE (as well as NetDRIVE).

Locally, I have been involved in the setup of an EPCC Sustainability committee, which is being chaired by Kirsty Pringle.

Key Outputs

	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
24–26 September 2025	Presentation on Champion role, best practice guides, and ISPACE project at NetDRIVE AGM, Durham.	https://zenodo.org/records/18174566 ; https://eng.ox.ac.uk/netdrive/events
8 October 2025	"A community approach for sustainable digital research infrastructure" – contributed to this video presentation on the NetDRIVE website.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17294360
5 November 2025	Presentation on "Environmental Sustainability of Services" at the UKNSR Towards Sustainable Digital Research meeting, Manchester.	https://www.uknsr.org/events/sustainable-digital-research-workshop-university-of-manchester
26 November 2025	Presentation on the "EPCC Environmental Sustainability Committee" with K. Pringle and A. Turner at the EPCC Seminar "Towards Sustainable HPC".	
16 January 2026	Presentation on "Environmental Sustainability of Services" at The Francis Crick Institute, London.	

Andy Turner — NetDRIVE Champion Update, September 2025–March 2026

Author: Andy Turner

Title: NetDrive Champion Update (Sep 2025 – Mar 2026)

During this first period of my NetDRIVE Champion project I have focussed on building connections out into the communities that overlap with high performance computing to

present on urgency of action and help build/deliver training to equip people with the skills and knowledge to be able to take meaningful action in reducing emissions from DRI. I have delivered two in-person courses based on the Green Software Use on HPC material I developed – one in Birmingham and one in London. I have presented at many different events with different audiences on action on emissions reduction from DRI in general and HPC in particular. Following the NetDRIVE Annual General Meeting in Durham in September 2025, I am part of the working group developing short format training for researchers on understanding and reducing emissions from DRI. I am working with Imperial College London to help them develop induction training for all researchers and RSEs on emissions from DRI and how to reduce them to help them achieve GreenDiSC certification. On the emissions understanding side, I have built links with researchers developing models of HPC emissions and am currently helping assess the EasyC model from researchers at the University of Chicago¹ for use in modelling emissions from UK HPC resources. This will feed into the NetDRIVE project I have had funded with another NetDRIVE Champion (Loïc Lannalongue) to develop a live emissions dashboard from UK HPC facilities.

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Key Outputs

Date	Description (including NetDRIVE angle)	Link
8 September 2025	RSE Leaders and Aspiring Leaders Meeting, Warwick University. Described why action on climate emergency from RSE groups is important.	https://rsecon25.society-rse.org/leaders-meeting/
10 September 2025	Green RSE SIG Meeting, RSECon25, Warwick University. Presented an update on HPC emissions training.	https://socrse.github.io/green-sig/events.html
16 September 2025	CoSeC Energy Efficient Computing Workshop, RAL. Presented on estimating emissions from HPC systems.	https://www.cosec.ac.uk/impact/a-multi-disciplinary-approach-to-embedding-energy-efficient-computing-practices-outcomes-
22 September 2025	ARCHER2 User Advisory Group. Summarised work on estimating emissions from ARCHER2.	
25–26 September 2025	NetDRIVE Annual General Meeting, Durham. Introduced planned work from Champions proposal.	https://zenodo.org/records/18174566

21 October 2025	UCISA Webinar, Cutting Carbon in UK Higher Education and Research. Presented on NetDRIVE project and Champions work.	https://www.ucisa.ac.uk/Events/2025/October/Digital-impact
22 October 2025	Green Software use on HPC Training, University of Birmingham.	https://epcced.github.io/2025-10-22_GreenHPC_Bham/
3 November 2025	Guest Lecture on HPC Emissions, HPC Architectures Module, EPCC MSc in HPC and Data Science, University of Edinburgh.	
19–20 January 2026	MCC VASP Workshop, LSBU. Case study of emissions efficiency of VASP software on different HPC machines.	https://mcc.hec.ac.uk/events/mcc-vasp-workshop-2026/
28 January 2026	MCC Annual Meeting (online). Case study of emissions efficiency of VASP software on different HPC machines.	
26 February 2026	Green Software use on HPC Training, Alan Turing Institute, London.	
18 March 2026	Championing Green Digital Research, ARCHER2 Celebration of Science Day 0. Three sessions: Green Software use on HPC; Estimating emissions; Lightning talk.	https://www.archer2.ac.uk/community/events/celebration-of-science-2026/day0

ANNEX C Financial Report and Expenditure Summary

Award Details

Field	Detail
Project	UKRI910: NetDRIVE2 – Network for Sustainable Digital Research Infrastructure Vision and Expertise
Award Holder	Martin Jukes
Organisation	University of Leeds
Funder	NERC
Start Date	January 2025
Duration	39 months
Award Value	£3,341,804.68

Resources and Costs Summary

Cost Component	Amount
Total Full Economic Cost (FEC)	£4,177,255.85
Total contribution from applying organisation(s)	£835,451.17
UKRI Indexation	£173,970.28
Award Value (80% FEC)	£3,341,804.68

The funding requested represents 80% of the total FEC, with the remaining 20% provided through institutional contributions from the participating organisations.

The full breakdown of costs is redacted from the public version of the report.